

TAKING STOCK OF COMMUNITY BASED CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN OIL & GAS COMPANY WITH MANDATORY GUIDELINES: CASE OF OGDCL IN DISTRICT SANGHAR

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Abstract

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a business approach that contributes to sustainable development by delivering economic, social and environmental benefits to all stakeholders. Despite significant economic and social importance, corporate social responsibility (CSR) in Pakistan has not been extensively researched. The Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Resources through the Director General Petroleum Concessions (DGPC) regulates and oversees the grant of permits, licenses and leases for exploration, development and production to exploration & production (E&P) companies. The E&P Companies operating in Pakistan are contractually obliged to make specified payments in lieu of exploration rights and privileges. The aim of this study is to assess the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) practices implemented in the surrounding community by OGDCL-Sinjhor field pertaining to DGPC social welfare obligations guidelines. OGDCL Sinjhor field is located near Rawtiani, 22.5 Km northwest of Sanghar in Sindh province. This study is based on qualitative research design whereby semi structured in-depth interviews and focused group techniques are used. The sample size for data collection comprises 20 focal persons from 20 villages who are living within 05 Kilometers premises of the OGDCL, Sinjhor-Field. According to the findings of this study the current CSR practices provided by OGDCL-Sinjhor field are insufficient in terms of health, education, environmental protection, infrastructure, and employment facilities. The study calls to policy makers for applying stringent implementations measures so that the corporate bodies aid and support the society in the matters such as education, health, environment, and raising living standards.

INTRODUCTION

The corporate social responsibility (CSR) emphasizes that companies have a role to play for society other than product manufacturing, providing services and making profit. The role of the companies may

include the social wellbeing of the society which directly affects the welfare of the community (Robins, 2005). CSR Can be defined as the set of practices and behaviors that firms adopt towards their labor

force, towards the environment in which their operations are embedded, towards authority and towards civil society (Foran, 2001). The proliferation of the CSR leads to an organized society and sustainable economy systems. CSR provides a framework for companies to have a positive impact on the society. Under CSR, the businesses need to manage their relationship with society whether for the social activities or adding value to the society.

The Islamic Republic of Pakistan is blessed with natural resources such as oil, mineral and natural gas. Through the Government and state regulatory authorities, the people of the country are the ultimate owners of these resources. In Pakistan more than 20 national and international exploration and production (E&P) companies are engaged in their activities. These activities of the exploration and production (E&P) companies have a disruptive effect on the surrounding communities where they operate. By keeping all these disruptive effects of E&P companies on the surrounding community into account these E&P companies have been obliged to consider the impact of their activities.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a voluntary contribution towards stakeholders and environmental sustainability, but the Government of Pakistan, by recognizing activities of these E&P companies, has incorporated provisions in contracts and officials policies, by setting out social welfare obligations guideline of these E&P companies operating in Pakistan. The Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Resources through the Director General Petroleum Concessions (DCPC), grant the permission of leases and licenses to E&P companies for the exploration of mineral resources, development of these extracted mineral resources

and the production and also it oversee the operations of these companies. These licenses specify the blocks which cover specific geographical areas. The present research study deals with contractual and legally mandated obligations of OGDCL-Sinjhero Field towards the community residing around the company where it is engaged in mineral exploration and extraction activities. This research aims at highlighting the social welfare obligations guideline given by DGPC to E&P companies firstly and secondly it aims at identifying the level of pursuance of this social welfare obligations guideline by OGDCL-Sinjhero field located in district Sanghar and its impact on the socio-economic development of surrounding community which comes within the 05 kilometers premises of the OGDCL-Sinjhero field Sanghar.

There are many definitions of CSR with different perspectives given by various research scholars and organizations, but there is no consensus on the definitions of CSR (Dahlsrud, 2008). Generally, CSR is defined as “the voluntary responses of organizations towards society beyond legal and economic activities”. According to the Carroll (1979), who is one of the earliest corporate social responsibility theorists, "in order to be good corporate citizen, companies have four categories of obligations towards society where their activities are embedded, the four obligations suggested by Carroll (1979) include economical, legal, ethical and discretionary” (see figure 1). The first modern definition of CSR as given by Bowen (1953), according to him “businesses are not merely responsible to generate profit and loss statements, businesses are also responsible for the impact of their activities on surrounding community”.

Figure 1. Carroll's CSR Pyramid (Carroll, 1991)

According to Votaw (1972), CSR is perceived in a different way by different persons. Some perceive it as a legal responsibility or liability while some perceive it as a social responsible behavior as a moral obligation. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (1999) issued a report on social responsibility in which CSR is defined as “firm and continuing commitment by

organizations to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of surrounding community as well as quality of the local community and society at large”. Jan and Baloch (2011) defines CSR as “set of ethical, legal and socio-economic expectations of society towards the business organizations operating within its premises”.

Theoretical Perspective (s)	Description
Agency Theory	CSR actions are mainly a result of self-serving behavior of managers at the expense of shareholders
Institutional Theory	Societal institutions play an important role in establishing a moral code for organizations
Resourced-based View	CSR is considered as a distinctive capability to produce competitive advantage for firm
Stakeholder theory	CSR is basically the result of establishing relationships with actors/entities which are influenced or can influence the business
Stewardship theory	CSR is driven by moral values/needs of managers to adopt right course of action without considering its effect on performance
Theory of the firm	CSR initiatives are driven by the market forces based on the assumption that it can produce social goods as well as strengthens company's position.

Table 1. Theoretical Perspectives of CSR

Source: Adopted from McWilliams, A., Siegel, D.S., & Wright, P.M. (2006)

CSR addresses the various issues related, i.e. employee relations; human rights; corporate ethics; community relations and environmental issues (Moir, 2001). McWilliams, Siegel and Wright (2006) gave many ideas of CSR that include; agency theory, institutional theory, resource-based theory, stakeholder theory, stewardship theory and theory of firm (see table 1). Likewise, Garriga & Mele (2004), discussed four types of theories in relation to CSR i.e. instrumental, political, integrative and ethical theories of CSR.

European Commission argues that CSR is beyond legal obligations as CSR practices are carried out for the sake of socio-economic development and in order to safeguard all stakeholders by allocating some amount from profit and adopting least harmful business operations. According to Carroll & Shabana (2010) CSR relates to non-profit activities of firms for the socio-economic development of the community beyond their economic interest. Jones et

al, (2010) defines CSR as “the activities of CSR help organizations in building soft image in society and getting competitive advantage that eventually helps firms to attract and retain new employees and customers”.

Corporate social responsibility is a form of self-regulating mechanism that requires corporations to be responsible in their business processes to all stakeholders to benefit society (Freeman, 2011). CSR is not about legal obligation it is beyond the compliance with legal obligations as it is long lasting commitment by the firms to benefit the society and all stakeholders. McWilliams and Siegel (2001) defined CSR as actions that appear to further some social good, beyond the law. Pierce and Madden (2010) (cited in Garavan and McGuire, 2010) defines CSR as a mechanism that improves the quality of the employees' life along with their families, and the stakeholders.

I. Human Rights
Principle 1: Businesses should support and respect the protection of internationally proclaimed human rights; and
Principle 2: Make sure that they are not complicit in human rights abuses.
II. Labor
Principle 3: Businesses should uphold the freedom of association and the effective recognition of the right to collective bargaining;
Principle 4: The elimination of all forms of forced and compulsory labor;
Principle 5: The effective abolition of child labor; and
Principle 6: The elimination of discrimination in respect of employment and occupation
III. Environment
Principle 7: Businesses are asked to support a precautionary approach to environmental challenges;
Principle 8: Undertake initiatives to promote greater environmental responsibility; and
Principle 9: Encourage the development and diffusion of environmentally friendly technologies.
IV. Anti-Corruption
Principle 10: Businesses should work against corruption in all its forms, including extortion and bribery.

Table 2. United Nation Global Compact – 10 Principles

Source: <http://www.unglobalcompact.org>.

The United Nation Global Compact (UNGC) is considered as the largest voluntary corporate sustainability initiative in the world. UNGC has more than 10,000 participants, including over 7,000 businesses in 145 countries around the world. UNGC has 10 principles on Human Rights, Labour Standards, Environment and corruption (see Table 2).

UNGC voluntary initiative aims at advancing the role of business in addressing climate change, the UNGC initiative has two objectives: i) to mobilize business on a global scale to take a stand on a low-carbon and climate resilient economy; ii) to inform the climate change global policy agenda and contribute to an appropriate intergovernmental climate change framework.

Exploration and Production (E&P) companies working in Pakistan whether multinational or national are obliged to follow the social welfare obligations guideline which have been given by Director General Petroleum Concession (DGPC). It

has been observed that E&P companies claim in their annual reports that they follow all given obligations in a proper manner by investing some amount decided by DGPC in surrounding community in order to develop it socially and economically. However, no development has been seen in surrounding regions where these E&P companies' activities are carried out. Therefore, this study aims at investigating the level of pursuance of DGPC social welfare obligations guideline by OGDCL-Sinjhor field in district Sanghar.

The aim of this research is to investigate the OGDCL-Sinjhor field's initiatives regarding socio-economic development of the surrounding communities pertaining to DGPC social welfare obligations guideline. The aim is achieved through the following research objectives:

1. To inquire into how many unskilled/non-technical employees have been employed from surrounding community.
2. To inquire into how many technical/skilled

persons have been taken from surrounding community.

3.To investigate the initiatives taken for health facility for the people living in surrounding community

4.To investigate the level of assistance in education.

5.To observe the steps taken for infrastructure development of surrounding community.

6.To investigate the initiatives taken for environmental protection.

7.To inquire about schemes for organizing sports event.

8.To know about initiatives taken for water supply/water purification

9.To inquire about steps taken for water drainage/sanitation.

This paper is structured in five sections. Next section is an extensive literature review about the CSR research in the context of Pakistan. It also explains the model deals with the issues about CSR in Pakistan and DGPC guidelines. Section 3 explore the case study of oil and gas companies in Sanghar district. Section 4 deals with conceptual framework of study as well as product and financial portfolio of OGDCL. Section 5 explains the research design including method, sample, population and data analysis techniques. Section 6 presents analysis results of research data and section 7 concludes the findings and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CRITICAL REVIEW OF CSR IN THE CONTEXT OF PAKISTAN

The study of Yunis, M. S. et al (2017) critically analyzed the literature available on CSR in the context of Pakistan. Their study indicates that most often the companies' practices of CSR are for short term, they do it as philanthropy or charity. Further they indicate that in Pakistan many researchers are just focusing on issues such as child labor in textile and leather industry. They suggest in their study that there should be focus of researchers on other issues as well.

The study by Kalhor, et al. (2017) highlights the CSR initiatives taken and as claimed by different companies in district Dadu. This study however depicts a totally different scenario. It identifies that although there were some CSR initiatives taken by

the companies but their sustainability in terms of maintenance and continuity is a serious issue. There is no any budget allocated for maintenance of the infrastructure provided to the community. It was observed that due to lack of CSR awareness of the local people, companies are not investing much in the community welfare.

Nadeem & Kakakhel (2016) conducted research to explore the practice, motivations and barriers to corporate social responsibility in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK). Their study concluded that SMEs do focus on CSR issues but they consider CSR as philanthropic contributions. In SMEs, main 6 categories are found with three categories of motivational factors such as: intrinsic, instrumental and stakeholder pressure. Managers of the SMEs said that the major obstacles in CSR practices implementation are: financial constraints, managerial skills and infrastructural problems.

Awan, et al. (2012) in their study identified the level of CSR practices of corporations. In their study they concluded that Pakistan has a moderate level of corporate social responsibility. They suggest that society, company and government should make an effort together in order to compel corporations to get better CSR practices. The Security and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) (2005), conducted a survey on CSR practices of companies in Pakistan. This survey highlights that mostly companies in Pakistan are doing CSR practices as philanthropic work and legal compliance. CSR is not being considered by these companies as a core value of their operations.

Many studies have been conducted on relationship of CSR practices and variables of financial performance in Pakistan. The study of Kiran et al. (2015) concludes that there is positive relationship between CSR practices and firms' profitability. The study of Kanwal et al. (2013) and Aga et al. (2012) also conclude positive relationship of corporate social responsibility and financial performance. While the research of Iqbal et al. (2012) highlights negative and non-significant relationship of CSR and firms' financial performance. Memon et al. (2017) conducted a research to investigate the link between corporate social responsibility concepts and firms' soft image. Their study concludes that there is a

positive link between firm image and CSR activity. CSR helps firms and their product as well in creating soft image and that soft image opens up more avenues for firms to stay in business.

Corporate social responsibility is not developed in Pakistan as it is developed in advanced countries. Corporate social responsibility is in developing phase in Pakistan. Some researchers have conducted researches on various firms such as the research of Kiran et al. (2015) is on oil and gas sector, the study of Javed et al. (2013) is on KSE-30 Index, the study of Iqbal et al. (2012) is on textile, chemical, cement and on the tobacco sectors. Malik and Muhammad (2014) conducted research on banking sector and Jan and Baloch (2011) conducted research on pharmaceutical industry.

A research was conducted and published by the Pakistan Centre of Philanthropic (PCP) on the CSR practices of publically listed companies of Pakistan in 2005. According to this survey based study, in Pakistan the CSR activities are done through donations. The real essence of CSR has not been understood in Pakistan yet. Ahmed (2006) claims in his study that in Pakistan the companies' major focus of CSR activities is employees' welfare and corporate philanthropy. His study also claims that the companies want to be good at financial performance. According to the Janda & Wilson (2006), in Pakistan context the terms corporate philanthropy and CSR are used reciprocally. Besides MNCs the companies in Pakistan take CSR practices not as an on-going process rather they consider it as a short term activity of charity

According to many scholars Asian business is far behind in many aspects of CSR than the western business (Dirany, et al. 2009; Low, 2004; Welford, 2004; Westwood & Posner, 1997). According to literature available it has been revealed that CSR level in Pakistan is below than CSR level in other countries such as European countries, American countries, Africa countries and other Asian countries.

(Salzmann et al. 2005). However it has been seen through literature that there is substantial improvement in few issues of CSR in Pakistan such as health and safety issues in leather and textile industry and child labor. (Ray, 1999).

The study of Sajjad and Eweje (2014) discussed the CSR status of Pakistani firms. Their study argued that in Pakistan the term CSR is new, many people are not aware about it but the good thing is seen that the interest and awareness regarding CSR is increasing day by day. According to Waheed (2005) and Khan (2012), in Pakistan the CSR is still a buzzword, firms and people do not understand the true concept of CSR. Most often CSR is considered as philanthropic activities. In real sense CSR is not a charity or any philanthropic activity rather it is a broad set of responsibilities which have to be delivered with commitment by organizations towards their stakeholders to safeguard them.

Naeem and Welford (2009) reported that in Pakistan CSR is still underdeveloped. They observed that public listed companies do good CSR practices comparatively to others. The study of Baughn and McIntosh (2007) also found low level of CSR in the organizations of Pakistan. Jeswani et al. (2008) in their study highlight that 75 percent of firms of Pakistan fall into the beginner category of CSR. Further their study observed that the organizations of Pakistan are prone to multiple challenges which cause hindrances and make difficult for them to practice CSR, challenges include: lack of regulatory framework, insufficient resources and lack of expertise.

The researches which are being conducted in universities and other institutions are less in number but it has been seen the number of these researches has increased. It has been interestingly seen in last ten years, two factors i.e. research (academic and non-academic) and pressure groups (Media, NGOs etc.) has focused on child labor in textile and leather industry (see figure 1).

Figure 2: CSR Issues in Pakistan

Source: Adopted from Yunis, M.S et al. (2017)

The figure given above has been adopted from the research study of Yunis et al. (2017). In their research they have reviewed thoroughly the literature available on CSR in the context of Pakistan. According to above figure it can be said that if academic researches, media and NGOs are focusing on any particular problem or on any specific firm sector, consequently business act and conflicting issues are resolved by business due to that pressure group (i.e. child labor from leather and textile industry is being abolished).

The figure suggests that various other issues such as social and environmental issues should be addressed by aforementioned two factors in order to be resolved. (Ahmad, 2006; Lund-Thomsen, 2004). On the basis of this study the research gap is also identified that there is also need to address other issues mentioned in figure which should be resolved and in other firms besides leather and textile industry.

2.2 DGPC SOCIAL WELFARE OBLIGATIONS GUIDELINE

The E&P companies working in Pakistan whether international or domestic are obliged to follow the social welfare obligations guidelines given by DGPC. DGPC works under the ministry of petroleum and natural resources, its main responsibility is to

regulate and oversee the activities of E&P companies working in Pakistan. DGPC gives permission to E&P companies through issuing licenses for exploration of oil, its development and production. Such licenses cover the particular geographical areas of different districts where activities are to be carried out.

As a standard practice a Petroleum Concession Agreement (PCA) is signed by E&P companies with government through the president of Pakistan. This PCA grants permission to E&P companies of exploration and production activities. The social welfare obligations which are to be followed by the E&P companies includes the appointment of skilled/technical persons from surrounding if available. E&P companies have to take unskilled/non-technical persons from surrounding and to train those employees. Non-technical persons such as: security guard, driver, peon, cook, imam of masjid etc. E&P companies have to take initiatives in several areas such as health, education, environmental production, development of infrastructure, water purification, sports activities and water sanitation.

The following clauses of the exploration license for petroleum concession area was placed by the learned Additional Attorney-General of Pakistan:

- 6)...
- (e) "The unskilled persons to be engaged as labour

should be taken from the inhabitants of the area particularly where the work has to be carried out with preference to displaced landowners. Rest of the man power will also be taken from the area if available. Locals of the area will be considered for grant of subcontracts provided their terms are competitive.”

(u) “The forest property will not be damaged and in case damage occurs during any survey, the licensees shall be responsible for it as per provisions of the Forest Act.”

(v) “The licensees will not use forest roads without permission. However, where the use of these roads is permitted, the licensees will be responsible for proper maintenance of such roads.”

zb.”Investment in social welfare schemes and training will be made in accordance with the provisions of the Petroleum Policy, 1997 [now 2012]. The licensees provide the manpower requirements (Category-wise) during different phases of operation to DG PC for approval.”

zd. “The licensees will strictly follow the environmental protection and pollution control laws and guidelines as notified by the Government from time to time.”

29.10 The Working Interest Owners, other than the GOVERNMENT HOLDINGS, shall be required, in consultation with local administration/Provincial Governments and the Ministry, to undertake schemes of Social Welfare such as: (i) To fight against narcotics, (ii) The promotion of sports (iii) Rehabilitation of the mentally retarded and handicapped children, (iv) Improvement of educational facilities, (v) Drinking water and health facilities (vi) Health facilities, (vii) Development of infrastructure, e.g. Roads. (viii) Grant of scholarships for local students and (ix) The company shall spend during the period prior to Commercial Production period not less than twenty thousand US Dollars (US \$20000) per year. (See Table.3) After the commencement of Commercial Production in the Area, the following minimum amounts will be spent during each year.

Production Rate (BOE/Day)	Amount/Year (US Dollars) For All
Less than 2000	20000
2000-5000	40000
5000-10000	75000
10000-50000	150000
More than 50000	250000

Table 3. Amount Spent based on Commercial Production

3. EXPLORAION & PRODUCTION (E&P) COMPANIES: A CASE of SANGHAR DISTRICT

The district Sanghar is one of the largest districts of Sindh province, Pakistan. It has an area of 9874 square kilometers. Sanghar district’s total population is 2,057,057 while its own city population is 75410. (see figure 3). Sanghar is situated in the center of Sindh province, it is roughly 35 miles to east-south-east of the city of Shaheed Benazirabad (SBA) and it has same distance to

Mirpurkhas which is located in its North side. India is located in the east of Sanghar.

The Sanghar district is administratively subdivided into six talukas: Sanghar, Tando Adam, Jam Nawaz Ali, Shahdadpur, Shahpur Chakar, Sinjhor and Jhol. Its primary industry is agriculture. Sanghar district is also known as the district of Hur Mujahid, who are the followers of Muslim saint Syed Shah Mardan Shah-II.

Figure 3. Map of District Sanghar

There are five exploration and production (E&P) companies, which are currently functioning in district Sanghar. In five E&P companies there are 3 OGDCL fields, 1 PPL and 1 UEP. OGDCL Sinjhoru field comes in Taluka Sinjhoru, this field is located at the distance of 22 kilometers from Sanghar. The second OGDCL field which is named as Bobi Oil field is located near Sanghar at the distance of 25 kilometers south of Sanghar.

The third OGDCL field is located near Tando Adam, about 20 kilometres away from Sanghar. The UEP field is located near Sanghar at the distance of 10 kilometres on Sanghar-Tando Adam road. The PPL field is situated near Shandadpur at the distance of 18 kilometres. The five E&P companies, working in Sanghar district are shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Map of E&P Companies located in District Sanghar

OGDCL-Sinjhoru Field

The Oil and Gas Development Company Limited (OGDCL) is located in Rawtiani. Rawtiani is the one

small city of Sanghar district and comes in Sinjhoru Taluka. The population of Sinjhoru Taluka is 320,874, whereas the population of Rawtiani is:

14206. The Sinjhoru E.L covering an area of 179.31 Sq.Km (approx.). It is a joint venture between OGDCL (62.5%), OPI (15%) & GHPL (22.5%) with

OGDCL serving as the operator. OGDCL has started to function with effect from Dec 29, 1999 for the initial term of ten years.

Figure 5. Map of OGDCL-Sinjhoru Field with surrounding villages

Sinjhoru development consists of a number of small fields discovered in the proximity of each other within the Sinjhoru Exploration License which includes: Baloch, Chak-2, Chak-63, Chak-63SE, Chak-66, Chak-66NE, Chak-7, Hakeem Daho, Lala Jamali and Resham. Sinjhoru gas field is currently producing at optimum level; a total of 26 wells have been drilled in Sinjhoru block. Out of these 26 wells, 10 are producers, 05 wells were shut-in and 11 have been plugged & abandoned. OGDCL-Sinjhoru field is surrounded by more than 20 villages which comes within 5 kilometers premises (see figure 5).

4. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 6 shows a research conceptual framework. In this conceptual framework it is highlighted that Director General Petroleum Concession (DGPC) which works under the authority of Ministry of petroleum and natural resources looks after the activities of E&P companies in Pakistan. The DGPC has given a clear set of social welfare obligations guideline to Exploration & Production (E&P) companies. This guideline has to be followed by E&P companies in order to benefit surrounding community where their activities are carried out.

Figure 6. Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher’s own work

According to this social welfare obligations guideline E&P companies are obligated to practice CSR activities in certain areas such as; appointment of skilled/technical employees, assistance in education, assistance in health, development of infrastructure, protection of environment, arrangement of sports activities, supply of water or purification of water for surrounding community and develop good drainage or sanitation system. This research aims at investigating the implementation of social welfare obligations by OGDCL-Sinjhero field in the surrounding community. The ultimate goal of this research is to investigate the impact of CSR practices on the socio-economic development of the community.

4.1 Product Portfolio of OGDCL

In figure 7 it can be seen that OGDCL produces four types of products such as Crude Oil, Gas, LPG

and Sulphur on everyday basis. OGDCL-Sinjhero is one of the major field as it can be seen in figure 6, Sinjhero field is producing three major products and helps OGDCL in generating huge revenue. According to OGDCL annual report 2018, crude oil accounts \$54.56 per barrel and total 41,278 barrels is produced every day which equals to Rs.351,317,058. Gas is produced 1,022 MMcf every day, 1 MMcf accounts Rs.258.93 and total amount of 1,002 MMcf of gas equals to Rs. 264226.46 for every day. LPG accounts Rs.55,666 per ton and 690 tons of LPG equals to Rs.38409540 for every day. Sulphur is produced 58 tons per day, 1 ton of Sulphur costs Rs.11,576 and 58 tons of Sulphur equals to Rs.1,077,408, this amount is generated on regular basis. If all amounts of all products produced on daily basis are added the total amount would be Rs.391,068,232 per day and monthly the total amount would be Rs.11,732,046,960.

Figure 7. Product Portfolio of OGDCL
Source: OGDCL Annual Report (2018)

Figure 8. Product Wise Contribution
Source: OGDCL Annual Report (2018)

Figure 8 shows the product wise contribution of OGDCL. The gas is produced in high quantity which accounts 49.49 percent of total 100 percent production. Crude oil is on second number production wise about 44.44 percent crude oil is

produced out of 100 percent. LPG is third in production which accounts for 7.7 percent and the other things like Sulphur etc. production is on fourth number in production which is 0.18 percent.

4.2 Financial Portfolio

Financials positions of the OGDC is reported in table 4. In this table it is shown that the

crude oil is measured in barrel and its one barrel is equal to 54.56 US Dollar, Gas is measured in McF¹, one McF of gas is equal to Rs.258.93. LPG stands for liquefied petroleum gas, LPG is measured in ton and 1 ton is equal to Rs.55,666 while Sulphur is also measured in ton as well, 1 ton of Sulphur is equal to Rs.11,576. Total assets amount 666.5 billion (in rupees). According to the Annual report 2018 of OGDCL, the total sales revenue is generated 205.3 billion (in rupees). The profit for 2018 is 78.7 billion (in rupees).

Crude Oil	Gas	LPG	Sulphur
54.56	258.93	55,666	11,576
US\$ per Barrel	Rs per Mcf	Rs per Ton	Rs per Ton
Total Assets	Sales Revenue	Profit for the year	Earnings per share
666.5	205.3	78.7	18.31
Rs in billion	Rs in billion	Rs in billion	Rs in billion
Total Dividend	Contribution to national Exchequer		
10.1	117.1		
Rs per share	Rs in billion		

Table 4: Financial Highlights (Net Realized Prices)

Source: OGDCL Annual Report (2018)

5. RESEARCH DESIGN

This research study aims at assessing the actual level of CSR pursuance by OGDCL-Sinjhor field pertaining to DGPC social welfare obligations guideline. This research is based on qualitative research method whereby focus group interview and individual interviews have been used as data collection tools. The sample for data collection comprises 20 focal persons, 1 focal person from each village. The selected 20 focal persons for focus group interview have been selected on the basis of information they have about their respective villages and are considered as most respectable and highly educated persons of their villages. The content analysis technique has been used for the analysis of data in order to generate research output.

¹ MCF is an abbreviation derived from the Roman numeral 'M' for one thousand, put together with cubic feet (CF) to measure a quantity of natural gas

5.1. RESEARCH TYPE

Qualitative research is a social or behavioral science research that seeks to explore the processes using exploratory techniques such as interviews, surveys and case study. This study is based on qualitative research method and the nature of this study is exploratory as it assesses the actual level of CSR pursuance by OGDCL-Sinjhor field, Sanghar district. Qualitative research method is a very helpful method which makes researchers able to understand the opinions of the selected participants deeply (Creswell, 2012). This method enables researchers to analyze the words which help a researcher to properly understand the opinions, perceptions and meaning of selected participants in order to generate knowledge and results regarding research question.

5.2. RESEARCH POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE

This research has been conducted in the Sinjhor, a taluka of district Sanghar. OGDCL Sinjhor field is located in Rawtiani village, which comes in taluka Sinjhor. The Sinjhor taluka consists of many towns, small and big villages. There are approximately 20 villages which come in the 5 kilometer premises of OGDCL-Sinjhor field. The sample size for data collection comprises 20 focal persons from 20 villages who are living within 05 Kilometers premises of the OGDCL, Sinjhor-Field. In qualitative research methodology, the sampling size or the number of the participants are not standardized, as this type of research works with a small number of sample of participants. Its context is dependent and its analysis is in-depth. In qualitative research methodology, the sampling techniques and sizes are different from quantitative research because, the purpose of qualitative research is not to count the opinions of the individuals but to explore the ranges of the opinions and different representations regarding issues (Gaskell, 2000). The sample size should neither be too big nor too small (Kvale, 1996). Sampling techniques can be divided into two main types: probability and non-probability sampling. This study is based on non-probability sampling techniques. Non-probability sampling depicts that the selection of each individual or the participant is not randomly selected but rather is selected by the researcher (Greener, 2008).

The 20 focal persons selected for this study are those persons who are well informed, highly educated and reliable persons of their respective villages. Moreover, in order to validate the selected data from 20 focal persons and to increase its credibility, other persons of twenty (20) villages except the participants of focus group have also been interviewed individually.

5.3. DATA COLLECTION TOOL

In order to gain the data from the sample, several research tools are used in Qualitative research such as logic, ethnography, disclosure analysis, case study, open-ended interview, semi-structured interviews, participant observation, counseling, therapy, grounded theory, comparative method and historical research (Cibangu, 2013). For this study, two data collection techniques namely: semi structured in-depth interview and focus group interview have been applied for the credible output of this research study. Semi structured in-depth interviews have been conducted from persons individually other than participants of the focus group interview. The focus group interview technique which is another important tool for the data collection has been used in this research. The semi structured interviews ranged from 15 to 20 minutes for each respondent interviewed individually and focus group interview ranged approximately 2 hours in which twenty focal persons from twenty villages have participated.

5.4 DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUE

Content analysis is a method to analyze the qualitative data that focuses on the context and subjects while accentuating upon the variations. Qualitative content analysis provides the opportunity to analyze latent, descriptive, manifest as well as interpretive content (Graneheim & Lundman, 2004). Content analysis as a data analysis technique has been used for this research. Most of the qualitative studies rely on the audio or video data collected through interviews, focus group, talks in consultations. The audio or video-recorded data are usually transcribed into written forms for further studies. The focus group interview that ranged 2 hours was recorded and then it was transcribed in a proper manner to get the results of this study. Semi structured interview conducted from individual persons were also recorded for the validity and

credibility of the data. After the transcription process the results were generated for the study.

5.5. LIMITATIONS

This research aims at analyzing the actual level of CSR pursuance by OGDCL-Sinjhor field, district Sanghar pertaining to DGPC social welfare obligations guideline. Firstly, I contacted to field manager of mentioned oil & gas field for an appointment so that I would have taken his interview and could have known about their initiatives regrading CSR in surrounding community but field manager denied to give me time for interview, even he said that they are not allowed to give any information regarding CSR. Afterwards I contacted to OGDCL head officer which is located in Islamabad, as per GM CSR manager I emailed him official letter issued by MUISTD for required data. I waited for 2 weeks and then phoned him again to remind him, he ensured me for sending data again, likewise I waited for 2 weeks but did not get any email or response from him. Similarly as before I phoned him again, he gave me previous same answer that he would send me data through email. I waited for many days again but could not receive data. Afterwards, I took OGDCL annual report from its website and saw its claim about CSR initiatives and then I decided to go in a surrounding villages to investigate the actual level of CSR pursuance by OGDCL Sinjhor field, district Sanghar.

6. DATA ANALYSIS

This research study is based on qualitative research method whereby focus group interview primarily as a data collection tool has been used in which twenty (20) focal persons each representing to his village respectively, has participated. The sample of twenty (20) focal persons was selected on the basis of their education, knowledge they have about their respective villages. Besides having good knowledge of their respective villages the selected persons are also considered as the most respectable persons of their villages. The focus group interview ranged 2 hours. The semi structured in-depth interviews have also been collected from the persons of the surrounding twenty (20) villages other than the twenty participants who participated in the focus group interview in order to validate the results obtained

from the focus group interview data and to make it more credible. After the collection of data through focus group interview in order to generate the results the content analysis technique has been used. In first step of the content analysis data was transcribed and then it was critically analyzed to draw results. Each objective has been described separately.

In focus group interview the participants were asked questions related to nine (09) objectives pertaining to social welfare obligations guideline given to all E&P companies by DGPC. The questions which were asked from the participants of the focus group interview are as follows:

- i. The first question asked from the participants was about the appointment of unskilled/non-technical persons from the surrounding villages in OGDCL-Sinjhero field.
- ii. The second question was about the appointment of skilled/technical persons from surrounding villages in OGDCL-Sinjhero field.
- iii. Third question was about the initiatives taken by OGDCL-Sinjhero field regarding health facilities to benefit the surrounding villages' people.
- iv. The fourth question asked from the participants of the focus group was about the education assistance given by the field to surrounding villages' students.
- v. Fifth question was dealing with the steps taken by the OGDCL-Sinjhero field for the infrastructure development in surrounding villages.
- vi. Sixth question asked from 20 focal persons was about the initiatives taken by OGDCL-Sinjhero field for the environmental

protection in terms of its sustainability.

- vii. Seventh question was about the sports activities organized by OGDCL field in the surrounding villages.
- viii. Eighth question which is second last question was asked to know which steps have been taken for water supply/purification and
- ix. The last ninth question was about the steps taken by OGDCL-Sinjhero field for water drainage/sanitation.

After conducting the focus group interview the collected data has been analyzed critically and result of each objective of this research study has been given separately on the basis of data. Before conducting the focus group interview all villages which come within the five kilometer premises of OGDCL-Sinjhero field were visited to know about the exact distance and population of the villages. During visit of villages, one person from each village on the basis of his education and information he has got about his village was invited to participate in the focus group interview to represent his village. One village namely Syed Muhammad Shah, which is the nearest and one person from this village is the president of the welfare union comprises all 20 villages' people helped a lot in data collection. The venue for the focus group was another village namely Pahlwan, where all invited persons for focus group interview gathered.

Table 5 shows the names of 20 villages with estimated population and their distance in kilometers from the OGDCL- Sinjhero field. Afterward result of each objective of this study has been given in sequence separately.

Village No.	Village	Population	Kilometres (From OGDCL)
01	Syed Muhammad Shah	150	0.5 km
02	<u>Khaber Khan Chakrani</u>	500	2.5 km
03	<u>Chaudhary Ilm Din Deh: 31</u>	450	04 km
04	<u>Karim Bux Chakrani</u>	40	0.6 km
05	<u>Raotiani</u>	5,000	01 km
06	<u>Allah warayo Junejo</u>	400	1.5 km
07	<u>Noor Muhammad Chakrani</u>	900	01 km
08	<u>Long Khan Chakrani</u>	50	01 km
09	<u>Hakim Khan Marri (Bhirri)</u>	3,000	02 km
10	<u>Pahlwan</u>	1,000	01 km
11	<u>Syed Imam Bux Shah</u>	1,500	2.5 km
12	<u>Haji Abdul Majeed Laghari</u>	500	01 km
13	<u>M.A Latif</u>	600	04 km
14	<u>Shah Sikanderabad</u>	2,000	04 km
15	<u>Muhammad Suleman Solangi</u>	200	03 km
16	<u>Suleman Chang</u>	1,000	4.5 km
17	<u>Kandero</u>	1,500	02 km
18	<u>Chak No.05 (03 Wells)</u>	19,000	03 km
19	<u>Faceerabad</u>	100	0.5 km
20	<u>Chaudhary Boota</u>	200	3.5 km

Table 5: Villages in the 5 Kilometre premises of OGDCL-Sinjhora Field

Source: Author’s own work

OBJECTIVE 01 & 02:

	Unskilled Persons		Skilled Persons		Total Appointed
	Available	Appointed	Available	Appointed	
Village No. 01	11	0	04	0	0
Village No.02	22	0	06	01	01
Village No.03	10	0	05	0	0
Village No. 04	12	0	01	0	0
Village No. 05	20	02	14	0	02
Village No. 06	30	0	08	0	0
Village No. 07	20	0	0	0	0
Village No. 08	08	01	0	0	01
Village No. 09	40	01	15	01	02
Village No. 10	50	0	10	0	0
Village No. 11	60	0	04	0	0
Village No. 12	10	01	0	0	01
Village No. 13	40	0	0	0	0
Village No. 14	400	01	25	0	01
Village No. 15	10	0	01	0	0
Village No. 16	35	0	10	0	0
Village No. 17	100	02	06	1	03
Village No. 18	100	05	19	0	05
Village No. 19	08	0	07	03	03
Village No.20	15	0	0	0	0
Total	1,001	13	135	06	
Total number of people who have been appointed in OGDCL-Sinjhora Field since Its inception					19

Description of Objective 01 & 02:

This study analyses the responses of 20 focal persons living in surrounding 20 villages of OGDCL-Sinjhor field. According to their responses and critical analysis of data there are 1001 unskilled persons available in surrounding villages in which only 13 unskilled persons have appointed in

OGDCL-Sinjhor field. However, 135 skilled persons are available from which only 6 persons have been taken from surrounding villages. Total 19 persons have been appointed. According to focal persons about 300 employees are working in OGDCL -Sinjhor field in which only 19 persons from surrounding are currently working there.

Geographical Representation of Objective 1 &

Figure 9: Unskilled persons (in percentage) taken by OGDCL-Sinjhor Field from surrounding community

Figure 10: Ratio of employees taken from surrounding community and total employees working in OGDCL-Sinjhor field.

OBJECTIVE 3:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 03:

According to the responses of 20 focal persons of the surrounding villages. OGDCL Sinjhor does not provide them any proper facility related health. According to focal persons there is only one dispensary within company in which no satisfactory treatment is being provided. According to them

dispensary provides only medicines without proper treatment, medicines does not belong to any well reputed pharmaceutical company. The big problem is that they provide medicines only on selected 2 particular days of week, without these two days they do not give any medicine.

Does OGDCL provide any health facility?

OBJECTIVE 4:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 04:

When surrounding residents were asked about educational assistance they unanimously said that no educational assistance is given to students. OGDCL claims that students are given school uniforms and scholarships to assist them in perusing good education, but no such initiatives regarding

educational assistance have been taken by OGDCL-Sinjhor field. Focal persons said only one bus for students' pick-up service is run but that is approachable only for those students who are living near main road, students who live away from main roads are in problem as they have walk a distance to approach bus, there is also a huge rush of students only in one bus which creates problems for children.

Is OGDCL providing any educational assistance to deserved students of the community?

Focal Persons	Response
Village No. 01.. to ... Village No. 20	No

OBJECTIVE 5:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 05:

When a question about infrastructure was asked from focal persons of the villages they were extremely

disappointed and they all were complaining that no infrastructure has been developed by OGDCL-Sinjhor Field. Not even single road of any village, which comes in the premises of 05 kilometers of the

mentioned company has been rebuilt or repaired. They are only doing green wash, they claim in their reports about the infrastructure development but the ground reality is that there is no any work they claim was observed there in surrounding of the

OGDCL-Sinjhor field. The roads of villages were developed 20 years back by the local government after that no scheme has been proposed for the repairing of local road which leads to their village from main road.

Focal Persons	Response
Village No. 01... to ... Village No.20	No

Has OGDCL-Sinjhor Field developed infrastructure in surrounding community?

OBJECTIVE 06:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 06:

In the focus group interview 20 focal persons of the villages when a question regarding environmental protection was asked they responded in a disheartened manner that no any scheme has been provided by the OGDCL which sustains the environment. Chimney discharges smoke entire day

in the air, consequently many people including children are suffering from many skin diseases and Asthma, no actions are being taken to cope up with these problems. According to focal persons instead of proposing new schemes they advise villagers to shift to another area for safety and avoid these problems.

Is OGDCL-Sinjhor Field taking any initiative for environmental protection:

Focal Persons	Response
Village No.01... to.. Village No.20	No

OBJECTIVE 07:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 07:

In the annual reports OGDCL claims that they organize sports activities or events for the residents who are living in villages in surrounding which come in the 05 kilometers premises of the OGDCL Field. When this claim of OGDCL was checked by asking

20 focal persons who were representing their villages, surprisingly their answers were shocking. According to all focal persons no such type of sports events are organized by the OGDCL-Sinjhor Field for the surrounding residing people. They said OGDCL is only making false claims

Does OGDCL-Sinjhor Field organize any sport event for the surrounding community?

Focal Persons	Response
Village No.01 ... to ... Village No.20	No

OBJECTIVE 08:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 08:

According to the analysis of answers of 20 focal persons, no steps regarding water supply or the purification of water have been taken yet. According to all of them many villagers are suffering from

various diseases mainly reason is contaminated water which villagers drink daily due not having facility of water filtration or water purification. While OGDCL claim in its reports that it is providing water supply or water purification facility to the surrounding residence.

Has OGDCL taken any step for water supply/purification of water?

Focal Persons	Response
Village No. 01 .. to... Village No. 20	No

OBJECTIVE 9:

DESCRIPTION OF OBJECTIVE 09:

According to the surrounding villages’ focal persons no sanitation/drainage system has been built by the OGDCL in the surrounding villages. They showed an open gutter in the main city Rawtiani, this city is

at 01 kilometer distance from the OGDCL-Sinjhero Field but the condition of sanitation was worst, villagers also claimed that OGDCL shows fake information about the sanitation and many other initiatives.

Has OGDCL worked on sanitation/drainage system in surrounding community?

Focal Persons	Response
Village No. 01...to..... Village No. 20	No

**7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION
CONCLUSION**

This research has analyzed the actual level of corporate social responsibility (CSR) pursuance of OGDCL particularly OGDCL-Sinjhero field pertaining to DCPC social welfare obligations guideline. The ministry of petroleum and natural resources through the Director General Petroleum Concessions (DGPC) oversees and monitors the activities of all exploration and production (E&P) companies working in Pakistan whether they are international or domestic. The social welfare obligation guideline given by DGPC is mandatory to be followed by the all E&P companies. In case of not following the given social welfare obligation guideline, E&P Company’s license can be suspended. The OGDCL claims in its annual reports that it is pursuing the DGPC social welfare obligations guideline in a proper manner to develop the surrounding community by taking initiatives in health, education, infrastructure, environmental protection, water purification, water sanitation and sports activities. Therefore, by keeping this DGPC social welfare obligations guideline into account this study aimed at investigating the actual level of pursuance of these social welfare obligations through nine objectives.

The focus group interview was conducted for the collection of data. In focus group interview twenty (20) focal persons of twenty villages participated, each focal person was representing his village. These twenty villages come in the within the five kilometer premises of OGDCL-Sinjhero field. All twenty focal persons were selected on the basis of their knowledge, they have about their respective villages. All selected focal persons for focus group interview are well educated and are also considered as the most

respectable persons of their respective villages. This interview ranged two hours. The semi structured in-depth interviews were also conducted from the people of surrounding villages of OGDCL-Sinjhero field, the informant were selected other the participants of the focus group interview. These interviews were conducted in order to validate the data collected from the focus group interview and to make data more credible.

The content analysis technique has been used for generating results. The recorded video of focus group interview was transcribed into written form to drive results. After the critical analysis of data gathered through focus group interview this study has identified that the actual pursuance level of DGPC social welfare obligations guideline by the OGDCL-Sinjhero field is not at satisfactory level. Nine main questions were selected from DGPC social welfare obligations guideline to analyze the corporate social responsibility pursuance level. According to the analysis OGDCL-Sinjhero field is having total 300 employees in which only 16 employees have been appointed from surrounding community including technical/skilled and non-technical/unskilled persons.

No particular initiatives have been taken by OGDCL-Sinjhero filed in all dimensions, claimed by OGDCL in its annual reports. The areas in which E&P Company has to take initiatives include: health, education, infrastructure, environment protection, sports activity, sanitation and water purification. According to twenty participants of the focus group interview in the area of health only one dispensary is being run within the boundary of OGDCL-Sinjhero field. In this dispensary, the people of surrounding are allowed only for two days of a week, these two

days only medicines are given free of cost without any proper checkup.

The focus participants claim that no educational assistance is being given to the students of surrounding villages. According to them merely one bus for pick-up service is being run by OGDCL-Sinjhor field and that one pick-up service bus is not enough for the huge number of students. This bus is only approachable for those students who live near main road, students who live in villages away from main road are in difficulty. According to the focal persons no scholarships are being given to the needy students of surrounding community in order to pursue the higher education. Besides these initiatives no particular initiatives have been taken by OGDCL-Sinjhor field in the development of infrastructure, protection of environmental, water supply/water purification, sanitation and in organizing sports activities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The conclusion of this study highlights the facts on ground level through the investigation from surrounding 20 villages' focal persons. The study concludes that no particular steps have been taken by OGDCL-Sinjhor field in the pursuance of DGPC social welfare obligations guideline. Through the achievement of nine objectives it has been seen that no socio-economic development has been observed in the surrounding community.

The DGPC should stringently monitor the level of pursuance of social welfare obligations of all exploration and production (E&P) companies on the ground level. There should be strict auditing to ensure the proper utilization of funds allocated towards schemes for the socio-economic development of the surrounding community. DGPC ought to take enforcement action against any company which is non-compliant with terms of a permit, license, lease, agreement and the rules so that social welfare obligations may meet in a timely and proper manner.

FUTURE IMPLICATIONS

The results of this research study highlight the actual level of pursuance of CSR practices by OGDCL, Sinjhor-Field Sanghar. In future research would be conducted on how much amount is allocated for

social welfare funds, where these funds are utilized and what are the barriers that OGDCL, Sinjhor-Field is facing in utilizing the social welfare funds.

There are five exploration and production (E&P) companies which are doing extraction in district Sanghar in which 03 companies are of OGDCL, 1 company of PPL and 1 company of UEP. This study focuses only on OGDCL-Sinjhor field further other remaining four fields should be analyzed as well to investigate their level of pursuance of social welfare obligations guideline in order to develop surrounding economically and socially.

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